

THE MODERN METHODS OF RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article deals with the great importance given to the modern methods of teaching the Russian language in the process of primary education, as well as the modern teaching methods necessary for learning Russian language.

Keywords: primary education, the Finnish teaching system, the method of signs and pictures, the method of voice recognition and adaptation, the method of learning with the natural world, the method of adapting one's activities to students.

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Primary education is the first stage of education and upbringing of our youth. The right early childhood education and training program should help our children grow and learn in ways that match their unique intelligence. But children, unlike adults, do not plan the future, tomorrow. Children learn Russian more easily by understanding stories or winning through games. If they want, they can strengthen their organ information through games with their participation.

On the one hand, the content expressed in language should be related to children's life and daily life, on the other hand, activities or tasks that invite children to communicate should be interesting and important. During the lesson, students understand themselves as a part of the lesson, and during the lesson, they behave and act like the characters of the play. In primary education classes, foreign language learning is usually very effective and successful when it is organized using action methods based on life situations and games.

If the Russian language is taught through game-plot situations, all children will participate willingly, because they feel that they are a part of the situation created in this way. First of all Students "live" with the Russian language in small classrooms. Therefore, communication in the classroom should be in Russian language. Children can not only understand the instructions, but also express their needs through the Russian language.

In this regard, it is useful to communicate with Russian-speaking people (whose mother tongue is Russian), and to invite them to the class. According to the constructive approach, children should learn the meaning of words and rules in

Russian as much as possible. It also helps them develop basic thinking skills. Like all students, children have different learning styles. Education for children takes into account all styles of approach. Tactic and kinesthetic types of learning require special attention from the teacher. Pupils' talents, skills, knowledge and interests are wider in primary schools.

Learning Russian also depends on the learner's ability to understand well. During the teaching of the Russian language, it is necessary to encourage each child for his actions. They should develop acoustic, kinesthetic, rhythmic and visual differentiation. Children are quick to organize, but quick to forget. Therefore, by repeating the speech several times, it is possible to help children remember it through games or handouts. Courses are spiral, and regular repetitions are an integral part. Successful foreign language teaching requires comprehensive methods. During the lesson, students' attention should be focused mainly on the content and importance of the language. Students should first of all focus on the content of the language. The successful teaching of foreign languages also depends on how skillfully the teacher uses the opportunities available to him. Pupils should be given tasks so that they are forced to apply and retain their organic knowledge in the course of the lesson.

Communication skills are important in the development of language skills. Social interaction, especially when students are able to apply the meaning of the language, enables them to use the language effectively. The teacher's ability to communicate and negotiate for this process is one of the main conditions for successful teaching. Russian language education should, first of all, encourage the organization of everyday, real knowledge and knowledge of a foreign language, but the development of specific knowledge should not be neglected.

Their interest is definitely related to the organization of the lesson process and the children's ability to achieve certain success in this lesson process. It is wrong to believe that this interest will remain the same throughout the years, therefore, pedagogues need to take care of it, that is, to ensure that the participants are happy and successful in the lesson.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it is necessary to say that primary education plays an important role in the development of our children. We need to provide them with modern technologies and modern education system. Primary education is of great importance for the development of the roots of every person in the society, that is, for them to grow up as children worthy of their motherland and strong individuals in the future. We need to pay more attention to the education of our children, create modern conditions, and help them learn through new methods.

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